

Use of sick pens in turkey farming

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Legal requirements

Council directive 98/58/EC concerning the protection of animals kept for farming purposes:

Any animal which appears to be ill or injured must be cared for appropriately without delay and, [...]. Where necessary, sick or injured animals shall be isolated in suitable accommodation with, where appropriate, dry comfortable bedding. (Annex; Pt.4)

Definition and impact on welfare

The sick pen is a designated area within a poultry farm, designed to temporarily house birds that require special care due to illness, injury, weakness or other health issues.

This space allows for the separation of vulnerable animals from the main group, thereby increasing the chances of recovery by reducing the risk of competition, aggression and, at the same time, minimising the spread of diseases and further deterioration of the physical condition of the bird in need of recovery.

Requirements for a functional sick pen

The sick pen must ensure the ideal conditions to promote rapid recovery, be functional and adaptable to the needs of the birds that may differ through the different phases of the farming process.

The sick pen must be **easily accessible** or **set up** when necessary, and clearly **identifiable**, with a distinct separation from the rest of the group. This area can be separated from the rest of the barn by masonry walls or set up within the barn, as long as sick birds are physically separated from healthy ones (e.g., with a metal mesh) (Figure 1). The materials used for the

construction of the enclosures and equipment that birds may come into contact with must be **non-harmful to the birds** and must be capable of being **thoroughly cleaned and disinfected** (Directive 98/58/EC Annex; Pt. 8). To prevent weaker or already injured animals lying at the edges of the sick pen from being pecked by healthy animals from outside, it is crucial that the bottom of the separating walls either is solid or consists of mesh with small openings (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Example of a sick pen set up inside a barn (© IZSLER)

The area designated for the housing of sick and injured birds must be easily **inspectable** and equipped with adequate **lighting** (either fixed or portable) to enable staff to promptly detect any signs of illness, stress or other issues. It is recommended to place the sick pen at the entrance of each barn, which reduces the distance that the staff must walk and simplifies management.

To ensure animal welfare and ease of management, the size of the sick pen should be tailored to the needs of the farm, which may differ through the different stages of the turkey production cycle.

Figure 2. Sick pen with identification sign and protection against pecking at the lower part (© IZSLER)

The **density in the sick pens** should be **lower than the density in the rest of the group**, e.g. at least 50% lower than in the rest of the group, to ensure the comfortability and enhance recovery. This means each turkey should have enough space to move freely, eat, and drink without having to compete for resources, avoiding overcrowding stress and reducing the risk of aggression, all in order to facilitate recovery.

Considering the intermittent use of the sick pen, it is advisable to create recovery areas using modular structures made of movable elements, which can be stored in adjacent rooms to the barn and quickly installed, **allowing for easy expansion of the sick pen when needed.**

Certain periods are particularly delicate and may require the **size of the sick pen to be adjustable.** Among these, the first period, when the animals are still in the brooding pens, is particularly critical. At this stage, errors in temperature or feeding management can trigger cannibalistic episodes, which require the immediate removal of the victims from the main group to prevent further damage or death due to cannibalism (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Episodes of cannibalism during the brooding period (© IZSLER)

Other periods of the rearing cycle that may require more frequent use of the sick pen are at around 35 days of age when the reddening of the bird's caruncles, snoods

and wattles trigger pecking attacks from conspecifics or towards the end of the fattening period when there is typically an increase in the number of lame birds that become object of cannibalism. These stages are particularly problematic due to increased competition and aggression among individuals (Figure 4, 5).

Figure 4. Pecking at wattles (© IZSLER)

Figure 5. Pecking at snoods and wattles (© IZSLER)

Feeders and drinkers must be easily accessible.

Existing equipment can be used, but additional feeders and drinkers should always be available for smaller and weaker birds, ensuring that all birds have access to feed and water. These should be positioned so that the birds can eat and drink without obstacles and without competing for the resources.

A dry, friable, and comfortable bedding is essential to maintain a healthy environment, as moisture can promote the onset of footpad dermatitis or other health issues.

Figure 6. Sick pen with the use of existing feeders and drinkers and low density (© IZSLER)

Identification of the birds to be recovered

Daily monitoring is essential to assess the health and well-being of animals. Regulation (EC) No 98/58 requires at least one check per day; however, more frequent inspections increase the likelihood of promptly detecting birds that need special care enabling swift interventions before their conditions deteriorate, improving their chance of recovery.

To ensure **all birds are monitored**, every accessible area must be inspected, including barns, verandas and ranging areas. An effective method is to walk through the barn in a transect pattern, preferably during peak activity periods, when healthy birds move towards feed while weaker birds lag behind, making them easier to identify. Since sick birds tend to hide in darker areas, it is crucial to carefully check corners, spaces under feeders and drinkers, as well as elevated structures (e.g., perches, raised platforms).

Recognising a sick or injured bird and determining the appropriate course of action for each case is a process that requires considerable expertise. For this reason, personnel responsible for animal care must have adequate knowledge and professional skills to make informed decisions.

To determine whether a bird can remain with the group, should be transferred to a sick pen or must be euthanised, it is essential to catch it and **assess its conditions**. If necessary, the decision should be made in consultation with the attending veterinarian.

The following signs may indicate health issues, pain or distress (non-exhaustive list):

- Lethargic, apathetic or overly agitated behaviour ;
- Dirty feathers;
- Compromised body condition (e.g., emaciation);
- Abnormal vocalisations (e.g., coughing);
- Closed or half-closed eyes;
- Ruffled feathers;
- Retracted head;
- Discoloration of the head or caruncles (pale, bluish);
- Presence of injuries;
- Walking difficulties (limping, joint swelling, leg misalignment);
- Malformations;
- Swelling of the head;
- Diarrhoea or faeces-stained cloaca (a sign of gastrointestinal disorders).

Birds that must be euthanised:

A bird should be euthanised only if there is a justified reason such as:

- Acute, unrelievable pain;
- Severe illness with no possibility of recovery;
- Inability to feed or drink independently, making survival impossible.

In general, when survival of a bird is no longer possible without severe pain and suffering, it must be immediately stunned and euthanised humanely, in accordance with the methods outlined in Annex 1 of Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009.

Birds that must be transferred to the sick pen:

- Only sick or injured birds with a real chance of recovery (e.g., minor wounds);
- Birds requiring individual monitoring and treatment.

In general, birds should be placed in sick pen only when, after an adequate recovery period, they can be reintegrated into the group or complete their life cycle without further pain or suffering.

Proper use of the sick pens

Mere separation does not constitute adequate care for the birds; therefore, frequent observation and the administration of appropriate treatments are necessary. If a bird does not show signs of improvement within a reasonable timeframe, following an expert assessment, it must be euthanised in compliance with Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009.

In general, birds that no longer require further monitoring or individual treatment, can eat and drink independently and are not attacked or disturbed by other birds may be reintegrated into the group. This is important to reduce competition in the sick pen and avoid that recovered birds may peck the less fit conspecifics. Cannibalism can also be reduced/prevented by the installation of hides for the more vulnerable birds within the sick pens.

In turkey farming, sick pens are widely used, as they enhance the chances of recovery for sick or injured animals when managed correctly. The decision tree in Figure 6 provides guidance to the operator on how to treat injured or sick birds.

Figure 7. Decision tree on how to handle injured or sick birds.

References

COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 98/58/EC of 20 July 1998 concerning the protection of animals kept for farming purposes.

COUNCIL REGULATION (EC) No 1099/2009 of 24 September 2009 on the protection of animals at the time of killing.

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